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PERCEPTION OF RURAL FARMERS ON THE EFFECTS OF LAND DEGRADATION ON AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY IN IMO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Despite several decades of effort to curb land degradation, the phenomenon has continued to negatively affect the quality of land particularly in eastern Nigeria. This study examined the perception of rural farmers on the effects of land degradation on agricultural productivity in Imo State. Specifically, the study investigates the type of land degradation in the study area, causes of agricultural land degradation, effects of land degradation on productivities and strategies for improving the degraded area. Multistage sampling technique was employed in the selection of one hundred and twenty (120) respondents. Questionnaire and oral interviews were the major instruments used for data collection. The data obtained for this study were analyzed using descriptive statistics. The results of analysis on the type of land degradation show that 58% of the respondents identified soil erosion as the main type of land degradation in the study area. Oil pollution was identified as the least type of land degradation. Results on causes of land degradation on agricultural land revealed that intensity of rain fall (45%) was the main driver of land degradation in the study area. All the items listed on effects of land degradation on agricultural land use and productivities in Imo state of Nigeria was accepted because all the items were rated high and had an acceptable overall discrimination score ($x = \geq 2.50$). The result showed that most of the respondent (53%) uses conservation method like cross-slope (33%) as one of the strategies for improving the degraded area, followed by terraces (8%), under agronomic method cover cropping (8%) ranked highest followed by mulching (6%) and the least was reduced tillage (3%). The research concludes that the roles of the people and the government should be complementary to achieve the best for the community in fighting this ugly situation caused by land degradation. Based on the findings, it was recommended that public campaign should be carried out by government agencies concerned on the importance of conserving or protecting land for future use.*

Keywords: Land, Degradation, Agriculture, Perception of Rural Farmers, Productivity

INTRODUCTION

Land and water are the most valuable natural resources and the whole agriculture sector

mainly depends on these two resources. Agriculture supports about 7.7 billion population of the world with food supply and

this indirectly put a lot of load on the land and water resources (Abhisheket *al*, 2021). The capacity of the agricultural sector to play its economic role has however suffered many setbacks in recent times. The rate of growth in the sector was far less than the rate of population increase. Higher demand as a result of population growth and urbanization, as well as the lack of alternative opportunities in rural areas, is putting pressure on agriculture to increase production, resulting in degradation of the land.

The phenomenon of land degradation occurs in different parts of Nigeria. Land degradation is induced by human and natural activities. The anthropogenic activities causing land degradation includes deforestation, overgrazing, bush burning, mining activities among others. Land degradation is a concept in which the value of the biophysical environment is affected by one or more combination of human induced processes acting upon the land. It literally refers to the impairment of natural quality of soil component of any ecosystem. Land degradation which is also seen as a decline in land quality caused by human activities, has been a major global issue since the 20th century and it has remained high on the international agenda in the 21st century (Imoke, 2012). Deforestation and land clearing for agricultural purpose, urban development and the slope steepness have been identified as the cause of wide spread erosion in many of the catchment basins of Imo State (Clement *et al*,2024).

Land degradation is the result of complex interaction among, physical, chemical, biological, socio-economic and political issues of local, national or global nature. Land degradation affects the economy and also has many negative impacts on agricultural productivity by reducing the fertility of agricultural land(Ephrem, and Isreal, 2021).

Land degradation is increasing in severity and extent in many parts of the world, with more than 20% of all cultivated areas, 30% of forests and 10% of grasslands undergoing degradation. Millions of hectares of land per year are being degraded in all climatic regions. It is estimated that 2.6 billion people are affected by land degradation and desertification in more than a hundred countries, influencing over 33% of the earth's land surface (Ephrem, and Isreal, 2021).

Land-use methods are regarded as the ultimate causes of degradation. Land degradation can be viewed as any change or disturbance to the land perceived to be deleterious or undesirable (Eswaran, 2001). However, the way this was undertaken, and the priority given to conservation, differs greatly. The use of erosion control structures such as Bench terraces, contour bank, contour ditches were localized (Imoke, 2012).

Land degradation is an insidious, gradual process of farmers may not easily perceive its severity. The smallholder farmers' decision-making procedures are strongly based on their perceptions of the forces that drive degradation (Tesfaye *et al.*, 2014; Haregeweyn *et al.*, 2015; Bewket and Teferi, 2009) and its consequences on their lives and livelihoods. Perception will partly control awareness, goals and practical actions. Local perception refers to the causes and status of land degradation as farmers detect and express it as occurring on their lands. Both perception and knowledge guides decision making and consequently, farmers' action on land conservation and adoption of sustainable land management practices (Bewket and Sterk, 2003; Amsalu and de Graaff, 2007). Interpretations of environmental change are culturally constructed and need to be thoroughly examined for a sound understanding of farmer behavior.

Land degradation poses a persistent challenge to ecosystems and sustainable livelihoods in

the state. It is a serious environmental threat in Imo state with its associated problems. Although government in the state has made several efforts to address land degradation problems, efforts being made has achieved little result, hence this research which seeks to examine further way of combating this ugly situation.

The broad objective of the study is to examine the effect of land degradation on agricultural farm land in Imo State. The specific objectives were to: (1) examine the types of land degradation in the study areas (2) explain the causes of agricultural land degradation (3) analyse the effects of land degradation on agricultural land use and productivities (4) assessthe strategies for improving the degraded area;

MATERIALS AND METHODS

THE STUDY AREA

Imo State is located in the south eastern part of Nigeria and lies between Latitude $4^{\circ}45' N$ and $7^{\circ}15' N$ and Longitude $6^{\circ}50' E$ and $7^{\circ}25' E$. The study area lies in the humid tropic with high relative humidity, atmospheric temperature, and rainfall. The mean annual atmospheric temperature ranges between $28^{\circ}C$ and $31^{\circ}C$ with February and April as the hottest months (NIMET, 2011). Mean annual rainfall range from 2500mm – 3000mm with the highest intensity observed between April and November (NIMET. 2011).

The study location covers three local government areas of Ideato North, Njaba, and Oguta in Imo State. Although the State is the third smallest State in Nigeria, it is however the fourteenth most populous with an estimated population of over 5.4 million as of 2022. The State economy is highly dependent on agricultural production, especially the production of palm oil. A key industry is the extraction of crude oil and natural gas, especially in Imo's north and west.

Figure 1: Imo State Showing the Study Area.

Source: (Department of Geography, Imo State University, Owerri, Nigeria)

SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

Multistage sampling technique was employed in the selection of sample. Three LGAs were purposively selected from Imo State (Njaba, Ideatu North and Oguta.) because they were highly degraded areas in the State. The next stage involved the random selection of two (2) communities from each of the LGAs. In the third stage, two villages were selected from each of the selected communities. Then, the last stage involved the random selection of ten (10) farmers from each of the twelve selected villages giving a total of one hundred and twenty (120) farmers as sample size.

DATA COLLECTION

Two major instruments used for data collection were questionnaire and oral interviews. The questionnaire was developed to gather information using scaling system. Values on the degree of agreement and disagreement to the questions raised in the questionnaire were allotted different scores as follows: Strongly Agreed (SA)= 4, Agreed (A) =3, Disagreed (D) =2, Strongly Disagreed (SD) = 1. The cutoff point was calculated as follows: $10/4 = 2.5$. Thus, response whose mean score is below 2.5 is not accepted as agreed and the responses from 2.5 and above are accepted as agreed.

DATA ANALYSIS

Data obtained were subsequently analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, charts and mean scores. Objectives (i) (ii) and (iv) were achieved using frequency count and chart and objective (iii) was achieved using mean score.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TYPES OF LAND DEGRADATION IN THE STUDY AREAS

The phenomenon of land degradation occurs in different parts of Nigeria. Land degradation is induced by human and natural activities. There is human induced land degradation as they can be prevented. This includes erosion, deforestation, oil pollution, overgrazing, bush burning and mining activities. Figure 2 showed the results of analysis on the type of land degradation in the study areas, which revealed erosion (58%) followed by flooding (18%), as the main types of land degradation found in the study area. This implies that erosion is the most serious indicator of land degradation according to the farmers in the area.

Also, the result revealed that deforestation (17%) is another type of land degradation found in the study area. Deforestation which is the removal of the natural vegetation for fuel wood, agriculture and industry is increasing at an alarming rate and this is causing serious problem due to lack of permanent vegetative cover. The least was oil pollution (7%) which is the accidental or deliberate, operational spills of oil from ships, especially tankers, offshore platforms and pipelines. Among the LGAs under study, it was only Oguta LGA that had this type of land degradation may be because it is one of the oil producing area in Imo State. Presently in Nigeria, oil spills regularly occur in the oil-producing areas of the country while gases are continuously flared in these areas (Onwuka, 2005; Platform 2006; Cohen, 2008; Udoetok and Osuji, 2008). These burnt gases are obviously continuously washed down to earth by rainfall to pollute the environment (Hani, 1994).

Figure 2: Types of land degradation in the study area
Source: Field survey, 2023

CAUSES OF LAND DEGRADATION ON AGRICULTURAL LAND

The results of the farmers' responses on the causes of land degradation on agricultural land are displayed in Figure 3. The data collected revealed that intensity of rain fall was the major factor that contributed to land degradation on agricultural land in the three LGAs (45%). This is in line with findings of Hammad *et al* (2021) who observed that abrupt changes in climatic factors, exploitation of natural resources, and land degradation contribute to soil erosion. According to Niacsuet *al* (2022), land degradation through erosion processes is probably the most restrictive issue regarding the sustainable agricultural use of land resources. Soil erosion has become a major

cause of land degradation with regrettable economic losses.

This is followed by population pressure (22%), which pushes farmers to cultivate on a steep slope and neglected lands in the area. Population increase has been one of the frequent causes of land degradation. There has been debate on relationship between population number, growth rate and agricultural development, particularly the intensity of farming system. That means as the number of population increase, the required land for agriculture, house hold construction and other activities increase. This lead so miss management of land without knowing their degraded form (Gok, 2002).

Figure 3: Causes of land degradation on agricultural land

Source: Field survey, 2023

Deforestation (17%), has been a major cause of land degradation which adversely affect agricultural productivity, the health of humans as well as of livestock, and economic activities. The study showed that 7% of the farmers recorded bush burning as one of the factor contributing to land degradation in the study area. The result further revealed that (3%) of the farmer mentioned overgrazing which is the overexploitation of vegetation for domestic use as one of the driver that contribute to land degradation in the study area followed by farmers' lack of information (2%), Land pollution (2%) and the least was urban sprawl (1%). This implies that many factors under the umbrella of degradation contributed to the loss of agricultural land and low productivity in the study area especially runoff. Soil erosion has been and continues to be a major threat to agricultural land degradation especially in Imo State. Ephrem and Isreal (2021), indicated that the major causes of land degradation include rapid population increase, severe soil loss, deforestation, low vegetative cover and

unbalanced crop and livestock production. In addition, topography, soil types and agro-ecological parameters are contributing factors in the degradation processes influenced by man.

EFFECTS OF LAND DEGRADATION ON AGRICULTURAL LAND USE AND PRODUCTIVITIES

All the items listed on effects of land degradation on agricultural land use and productivities in Imo state of Nigeria were accepted because all the items like: plant yield declines, reduce global agricultural production, depletion of soil fertility, vegetation becomes increasingly scarce, reduction in land size, weaken the structure and even change the texture and footpaths grow into gullies respectively, were rated high and had an acceptable overall discrimination score ($x = \geq 2.50$). This implies that land degradation has effect on agricultural land and productivity. This was in line with the findings of Berry, (2003) who maintained that land degradation manifests itself in many different ways: vegetation becomes

increasingly scarce, water courses dry up, thorny weeds predominate in once rich pastures, footpaths grow into gullies, and soils become thin and stony. All of these manifestations have potentially severe impacts on the environment, for land users and for people who rely for their living on the products from a healthy landscape (Berry, 2003).

When soil is eroded basic plant nutrients such as; nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and

calcium also lost. Eroded soil typically contains about the three times more nutrient than the soil left behind on the eroded land (Lat, 2001). Once the organic matter layer is depleted the productivity of the ecosystem as measured by crop yield declines. Plant yield declines both because of the degraded soil structure and depletion of nutrients contained in organic matter (Lat, 2001).

Table 1: Effects of land degradation on agricultural land use and productivity

ITEMS	SA		A		D		SD		Total Score	Mean Score
	4		3		2		1			
	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score	F	Score		
Plant yield declines	70	240	30	90	12	24	8	8	364	3.017
reduce global agricultural production	20	80	50	150	35	70	15	15	315	2.625
depletion of soil fertility	80	320	30	90	8	16	2	2	428	3.567
vegetation becomes increasingly scarce	30	120	80	240	2	2	8	8	370	3.083
Reduction in land size	90	350	20	60	7	14	3	3	427	3.558
weaken the structure and even changes the texture	15	60	90	270	5	10	10	10	350	2.917
footpaths grow into gullies	30	120	80	240	2	2	8	8	370	3.083

Key; SA: Strongly Agreed; A: Agreed; SD: Strongly Disagreed; D: Disagreed; SD Key; SA: Strongly Agreed; A: Agreed; SD: Strongly Disagreed; D: Discriminatory index: Cut off point ≥ 2.50 , F = Frequency.

Source: Field survey, 2023

STRATEGIES FOR IMPROVING THE DEGRADED AREA

The result showed that majority of the respondent (53%) uses conservation method like cross-slope (33%) as one of the strategies for improving the degraded area, followed by terraces (8%) (See Table 2). Under agronomic method (35%), cover cropping (8%) ranked highest followed by mulching (6%) and the least was reduced tillage (3%). Other methods that can be used to improve the condition of degraded land as identified by respondents include adding nutrients to degraded soil (6%),

buffering soil acidity (4%) and rebuilding topsoil through soil amendments (2%). All these techniques are already in use in the study area to combat the ugly situation of land degradation in Imo State. This is in line with Muhammad and Mustapha (2020), findings that smallholder farmers employed knowledge-based procedures and methods of maintaining land systems over the indefinite future improved land productivity. Most of the farmers were commonly using agronomic/biological conservation measures to handle land degradation in the study area.

Table 2: Strategies for improving the degraded area

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Sub ground total
Under agronomic method,			35
Cover cropping	9	8	
Mulching	7	6	
Reduced tillage	4	3	
Crop rotation	6	5	
Planting of tree crop	16	13	
Conservation method			53
Cross-slope	40	33	
Terraces	10	8	
Bunds	8	7	
Vegetation strips	6	5	
Other methods			12
Adding nutrients to degraded soil	7	6	
Buffering soil acidity	5	4	
Rebuilding topsoil through soil amendments	2	2	
Total	120	100	100

Source: Field survey, 2023

Land degradation can be prevented through different mechanisms depending on the nature and form of degradation. Soil erosion remains a key challenge for agriculture in several countries. Proper management of this valuable resource is vital to sustain long-term agricultural productivity. Soil conservation practices are tools the farmer can use to prevent soil degradation and build organic matter. These practices include crop rotation, reduced tillage, mulching and cover cropping and cross-slope farming is man controlling methods for the cause and impact of land degradation (Ephrem and Isreal, 2021). According to Clement *et al* (2024), accurate estimation of soil loss will provide reliable information in the management and mitigation solutions to soil erosion.

CONCLUSION

Natural phenomenon like land degradation is occurring in many areas of the world, affecting farm lands and productivity. Imo state, Nigeria is not left out in this problem; land degradation has made farmers in the state to live in fear of running the risk of poor farm productivity. The phenomenon of land degradation comes in different forms including massive soil fertility depletion, erosion, oil spillage, over grazing among others.

Land degradation induces disastrous impact on the socio-cultural environment and ecological setting of the country and especially in Imo state, the study area. The major causes include erosion, oil pollution, rapid population increase, severe soil loss, deforestation, low vegetative cover and over grazing. In addition, topography, soil types and agro-ecological parameters are contributing factors in the degradation processes influenced by man.

Land degradation cannot be underrated and the task of seeking solutions to the menace should

be a joint venture among all stakeholders. The researcher therefore conclude that both individual and government should be complementary in their role of combating this menace of land degradation in order to promote self-sufficiency in food production, not only for the communities but also for the country at large. For degradation problem to be tackled effectively, aggressive mass campaign and awareness must be mounted in the study area. Public campaign should be mounted by the governmental agencies and allied bodies on the urgent need on soil and land conservation methods if sustainable agricultural production is to be achieved. Other recommendations that can be considered include:

1. Regular public campaigns should be carried out by government agencies responsible. This is highly germane as every member of the society ought to know the importance of the need to protect land.
2. Farmers need to be educated on the implication of planting leguminous hedges on borders and in rows of their farms in order to control velocity of running water and reduce runoff.
3. There is need for government and non-governmental agencies to work with residents to enforce rules and guidelines aimed at reducing the rate of deforestation.
4. Residents of the study area needs to be empowered to embark on intensive sustainable agricultural practices rather than extensive practices in order to curb the flagrant clearing of forest for agricultural expansion.
5. Government should make attempt to employ the services of well trained and experienced erosion engineers and consultants in contracts aimed at solving degradation problems.

6. Government at various levels should promote forest plantations by making use

of vacant and unused lands to reduce land degradation induced by human activities.

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